

URBAN GREEN CHARACTERISTICS OF RESIDENTIAL AREAS IN THESSALONIKI GREECE, USING HIGH RESOLUTION SATELLITE IMAGES

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Abstract: The presence of green spaces in urban areas has become a vital parameter for the sustainability of an urban environment. Besides the vital role of providing fresh air supply and cooling effect, urban green areas are related to the reduction of air pollution and noise levels and their positive impacts in human health. On account of this asset, the observation of green space throughout the years in an urban environment can provide vital information about its quality. To this direction, this study aims at extracting urban green characteristics of Thessaloniki in Greece, using two high resolution satellite images with different acquisition dates. The Normalized Difference Vegetation Index was used in order to extract urban green from the two images. Furthermore, spatial statistics procedures were introduced in order to extract additional spatial indices. In order to assess in detail the urban green space within each residential district, additional GIS information for district neighbourhood boundaries was used. The results highlighted the areas where urban green has diminished through the years, as well as have provided a useful tool for evaluating each district by its urban green characteristics.

Keywords: Remote Sensing, Geographical Information Science and Systems, Spatial Analysis

1. Introduction

Environmental quality in the big cities represents a vital problem both for the individual as well as for the community. This is because the urban environment is strongly artificial and sometimes depreciated in comparison to the characteristics of the natural environment where the respective town developed. As an holistic concept, urban environmental quality comprises of multiple hazards such as noise and air pollution or insufficient presence of the natural environment. This paper examines the case of urban green spaces.

2. Study area and data

The urban complex of Thessaloniki, a typical Greek city, constitutes the study area. In this area, the land uses, where green space is found, are classified as follows (Matziris, 2011): a) private rooms (habitable spaces, front yards, facades, roofs etc, commercial premises and industrial premises) b) areas with special management regime (such as Campus, archaeological sites, camp sites, etc.) and c) public places (amusement parks, walkways, sidewalks, etc.). Green spaces in the urban complex of Thessaloniki are characterized by the limited extent due to excessive construction activity. From observation of the few modular spaces (traffic islands,

neighbourhood squares and parks), the absence of small open spaces and gardens between residences is evident. What is also obvious is the lack of sidewalks and large parks district, suburban parks and groves that could serve large numbers of city residents.

In this study, two satellite images were used in order to study the green spaces: one fused image from QuickBird Satellite, with spatial resolution 1m, acquired on 2003 and one fused image from WorldView-2 Satellite with spatial resolution 0.5m, acquired on 2010. Both images depict the city of Thessaloniki.

3. Application of Normalized Difference Vegetation Index in urban complex

The normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) is historically one of the first Vegetation Indices, that can be used to analyse remote sensing measurements and assess whether the target being observed contains live green vegetation or not. It is a normalized ratio of the NIR (near infrared) and red bands (Rouse, 1974).

$$NDVI = \frac{NIR-RED}{NIR+RED} \quad (Eq. 1)$$

In detail, NDVI is a band-ratio technique which produces a raster model that estimates the degree of photosynthetically active vegetation within each pixel. Values in this dataset range between -1 and 1, where -1 represents non photosynthetically active vegetation and 1 represents a high degree of photosynthetically active vegetation. (Birky 2001), (Wang et al. 2005)

In this case, the black and white images depicting NDVI values for the study area were produced using the proper algorithm with the Model Maker tool from the ERDAS Imagine (v.9.2) Software. After completing the necessary checks on the images and identifying which values correspond to vegetation, areas of vegetation are isolated and extracted. This is accomplished by applying proper thresholds for the values of NDVI using again the model maker tool. Figure 1 shows the final results of this procedure, where the extracted classes of green spaces are overlaid on the original multispectral images. (Fig. 1)

Figure 1. Extraction of urban green spaces from a. QuickBird satellite image b. WorldView-2 satellite image.

4. Change Detection for green spaces using spatial statistics

Since green space was extracted for two different dates for the study area, spatial analysis using spatial statistic tools can be applied in order to assess and estimate the degree of change

for the green areas through time. Using Spatial Statistics Tools in ArcGIS the geographical Mean Center of green space for both dates was calculated. Mean center is a point constructed from the average x and y values for the input feature centroids (in this case the input features are the extracted green spaces from the satellite images)

$$\bar{X} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n x_i}{n} \text{ (Eq.2)} \quad \bar{y} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n y_i}{n} \text{ (Eq. 3)}$$

Where x_i, y_i are the coordinates of the green space features and n is the total number of green space features.

Figure 2 depicts the derived mean centers for both images. (Fig. 2) It is observed that these two mean centers are very close to each other. This means that there is no significant change of green space from 2003 to 2010, only a small displacement which can be explained by the development of green space in the east coastal front of the city. In order to have a more detailed analysis, the same procedure was applied separately for every residential district of the city (Fig. 3). The analysis highlighted areas where significant change in green space was occurred (for example in the port area and in the east coastal front where green spaces were created, or close to the newly built City Hall were green space was replaced by buildings)

Figure 2. Mean center of green spaces from QuickBird (grey color) and from WorldView-2 (black color)

Figure 3. Mean center of green spaces from QuickBird (grey color) and from WorldView-2 (black color) for every residential district

Another spatial statistics measurement in order to compare the green space through time was the computation of urban green density (Stamou et al. 2012). Urban green density is calculated as the ratio of the observed urban green (in m^2) in the area of interest with the total amount of land of the area (in m^2):

$$\text{urban green density} = \frac{\text{urban green area}(m^2)}{\text{total amount of land}(m^2)} \text{ (Eq. 4)}$$

The following figure shows the results of urban green density for every residential district of Thessaloniki. (Fig. 4)

Figure 4. Graphical distribution of Urban green density a. for QuickBird(2003), b. for WorldView-2 image(2010)

The results reveal that the percentage of green space density for both dates is small, compared to international standards. This shows also that the urban planners have not adapted an urban policy in order to improve the conditions within the urban environment.

5. Results and conclusions

Analysing the NDVI application results in ArcGIS it is concluded that every designated green spaces are identified from the satellite image processing. This means that a fully automated process, without field measurements, can highlight and pinpoint the exact location not only of all designated green spaces, but also other spaces that are green areas but they are not characterised as public green spaces (private lawns, uncovered plots, uncovered schools or other facilities with limited use). Moreover, spatial analysis using spatial statistic tools was applied in order to assess and estimate the degree of change for the green areas through time. It is observed that there is no significant change of green space from 2003 to 2010. Additionally, the results of urban green density for every residential district of Thessaloniki for both dates reveal that the available green space does not meet the international standards for urban green space. Furthermore, the majority of the extracted urban green spaces has area which is smaller than 0.1 ha, as a result of the insufficiency of local government strategies and lack of macro implementation of urban policies in Greece.

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